

Eastern Apache

also known as “Chiricahua Apache”

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Anj Droë, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Religious Group, Native American (North American) Religions

The Central Band of the Eastern Apache are a Native American group residing in what is now New Mexico. This entry focuses on ethnographic evidence that reconstructs Eastern Apache life and beliefs in 1870, prior to the reservation era, at which time the Eastern Apache occupied territory west of the Rio Grande in what is now southern Arizona and New Mexico. The second half of the 19th century was marked by violent conflict between the United States government and the Eastern Apache, which ended in 1886 with the surrender of the Eastern Apache chief, Geronimo, to United States forces. Following his surrender, the Eastern Apache people were considered prisoners of war and imprisoned first in Florida, then in Alabama, and lastly, in Oklahoma. The combination of violence, imprisonment, and forced migration resulted in severe population loss among the Eastern Apache. In 1913, most of the Eastern Apache were again transferred, this time to the Mescalero Reservation in New Mexico (Beierle, 2012:2). In 1870, the Eastern Apache lived in autonomous settlements that engaged in warlike raids of both external societies and other Eastern Apache communities. Eastern Apache religion centered around the personal relationship that each individual had with a supernatural, animating principle known as “the power.” Those with especially strong relationships with the power were known as shamans. Power was believed to come from different supernatural sources, including one of many supernatural beings, and could be used for multiple reasons, from curing to cursing people. For the Eastern Apache, religious beliefs were inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life. Therefore, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society at large.

Date Range: 1855 CE - 1880 CE

Region: Central band, ca. 1870

Region tags: United States

Central band, Arizona and New Mexico, United States, ca. 1870

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research.

– Source 2: Murdock, George P. 1962-1971. Ethnographic Atlas. Ethnology 1-10.

– Source 3: Murdock, George P., and Suzanne F. Wilson. 1972. "Settlement patterns and community

organization: Cross-cultural codes 3." *Ethnology* 11(3): 254-295.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=nt08-000>
- Source 1 Description: Beierle, John. 2012. "Culture Summary: CHIRICAHUA APACHE." New Haven: Human Relations Area Files.
- Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=nt08-001>
- Source 2 Description: Opler, Morris Edward. 1941. *An Apache Life-Way: The Economic, Social, and Religious Institutions of the Chiricahua Indians*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of scriptures.

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "Missionary teachings concerning the importance of the Bible have been registered in the folklore too" (Opler, 1941:198).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (Resolved Rating), "Internal warfare seems to be absent or rare" (original code = 1) (Ember and Ember 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (Resolved Rating), "External warfare seems to occur almost constantly and at any time of the year" (original code = 5) (Ember and Ember, 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972, Column 6, Large or Impressive Structures), "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972:259,271; note: equivalent to SCCS variable 66).

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 2500

Notes: "A general estimate of Chiricahua population in 1850 was 3,000, reduced by disease and warfare to a little over 2,500 during the period of 1866-1874" (Beierle, 2012:1).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Membership is consequently assumed to be assigned at birth.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Therefore, it is assumed that the religion has political support.

Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 757, Political and Religious Differentiation, the head of the polity and the head of the religion are distinct (Ross, 1983; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: "This 'holy home' [of the power] is of the greatest religious significance to the shaman" (Opler, 1941:204). The supernatural home of the power is located "within or near some well-known landmark" (Opler, 1941: 204).

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: "Besides the homes of the Mountain People [non-human supernatural beings], places with markings on the walls or on rocks may be considered sacred" (Opler, 1941:312).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The major religious leader among the Chiricahua was the shaman (diyin) who received supernatural power in visions and dreams through the medium of familiar beings and objects, such as animals, plants, and celestial bodies" (Beierle, 2012:7)

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: "The major religious leader among the Chiricahua was the shaman (diyin) who received supernatural power in visions and dreams through the medium of familiar beings and objects, such as animals, plants, and celestial bodies" (Beierle, 2012:7)

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: "It seems that these powers select for themselves. Perhaps you want to be a shaman of a certain kind, but the power doesn't speak to you" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:202).

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: "If [the shaman] feels that his power is dissatisfied with him or that it is deserting him, he journeys to this place to pray and to receive some reassuring sign" (Opler, 1941:204).

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Obligatory for some

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the first pilgrimage is necessary to become a shaman: "The first trip to the holy home is the means, often, by which the power tests the faith of the novice and determines whether he is the kind of an individual through whom it should work" (Opler, 1941:204).

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "Missionary teachings concerning the importance of the Bible have been registered in the folklore too" (Opler, 1941:198).

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (Resolved Rating), "Internal warfare seems to be absent or rare" (original code = 1) (Ember and Ember 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

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Does the religion have official political support

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Notes: According to SCCS Variable 757, Political and Religious Differentiation, the head of the polity and the head of the religion are distinct (Ross, 1983; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Size and Structure

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Scripture

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– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of scriptures.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972, Column 6, Large or Impressive Structures), "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972:259,271; note: equivalent to SCCS variable 66).

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

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"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

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Notes: "Besides the homes of the Mountain People [non-human supernatural beings], places with markings on the walls or on rocks may be considered sacred" (Opler, 1941:312).

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Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "When a person is very sick and is unconscious, it is said that he is somewhere else, that his ghost has gone where the dead people are, to visit his friends. If he regains consciousness, it is because his ghost gets back again, and when he gets well he may tell where he was" (Opler, 1941:477).

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the spirit can travel separately from the body: "When a person is very sick and is unconscious, it is said that he is somewhere else, that his ghost has gone where the dead people are, to visit his friends. If he regains consciousness, it is because his ghost gets back again, and when he gets well he may tell where he was" (Opler, 1941:477).

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the spirit can travel separately from the body: "When a person is very sick and is unconscious, it is said that he is somewhere else, that his ghost has gone where the dead people are, to visit his friends. If he regains consciousness, it is because his ghost gets back again, and when he gets well he may tell where he was" (Opler, 1941:477).

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: "The most obvious evidence that the Thunder People are displeased with an individual occurs when he is actually struck by lightning" (Opler, 1941:240).

Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: "'If you don't worship them in the right way, you should be frightened.' . . . The restrictions are obeyed, not from fear of the power of those dancing [impersonating the Mountain Spirits],

but because 'the real Mountain Spirits could bring on sickness or death if these things were violated'" (Opler, 1941:112).

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "In the eyes of his fellows the moral person is one who heeds the social conventions and discharges his obligations in obedience to the tribal ethic" (Opler, 1941:458).

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that both previously human spirits and non-human supernatural beings are present (Opler, 1941:199, 302). See questions below for details.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: "The Chiricahua had a vague, personified belief in a supernatural being called 'Life Giver', who was sometimes pictured as a sky god. Occasionally prayers were directly addressed to him, but he was otherwise not involved in ceremonies" (Beierle, 2012:7).

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: "The Chiricahua had a vague, personified belief in a supernatural being called 'Life Giver', who was sometimes pictured as a sky god" (Beierle, 2012:7).

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, High Gods, a supreme high god is absent or not reported (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 34).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The ghosts are of two kinds—those of enemy peoples and those of tribesman (often of deceased relatives)" (Opler, 1941:302).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "... all owls are ghosts ..." (Opler, 1941:231). Because owls can be seen, it can be assumed that previously human spirits can be seen in some form.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "These 'words' of the owl can cause sickness through fright . . ." (Opler, 1941:230).

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: Evidence indicates that previously human spirits remember where they lived: "Another story, so well known that it has been recorded from four different informants, concerns the return of a woman's ghost to her former home . . ." (Opler, 1941:231).

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: "Owls [connected or equated with ghosts] talk the Chiricahua language. They say different things to different people" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:230).

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: "Owls [connected or equated with ghosts] talk the Chiricahua language. They say different things to different people" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:230).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "There are two other sets of supernaturals—the Mountain People and the Water Beings. The Mountain People are of more importance than any supernaturals so far mentioned, with the possible exception of Child of the Water and White Painted Woman" (Opler, 1941:199).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: Mountain People cannot be seen: "We hear words in there when we listen at cliffs or mountains, but we can't see the people" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:199). No ethnographic evidence indicates that other non-human supernatural beings can be seen.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "The Thunder People send lightning to punish some" (Opler, 1941:195).

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: "If people believe and learn his [Water Controller's] song, they can get rain" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:199).

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: "The Thunder People send lightning to punish some" (Opler, 1941:195).

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "However, fright [caused by the Thunder People] is again a powerful sickening agent: 'The scare harms you.' Lightning is said to be accompanied by an odor which comes from the powder or smoke that arises where it strikes. This powder, if it is inhaled, manifests itself in the ailment recognized as 'lightning sickness'" (Opler, 1941:240).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "The most obvious evidence that the Thunder People are displeased with an individual occurs when he is actually struck by lightning" (Opler, 1941:240).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that both previously human spirits and many different non-human supernatural beings are present. See Opler, 1941:199, 302 for more information.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: White Painted Woman is the mother of Child of the Water (referred to as the folk hero in the principal authority), who also has some type of kin relationship to Killer of Enemies, usually a brother. These supernatural beings are no longer considered active in human affairs (see Opler, 1941:197, 281).

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: The Mountain People protect the Eastern Apache from disease and enemies (Opler, 1941:267-268) and live in the mountains (Opler, 1941:35), the Water Beings have various powers associated with water (Opler, 1941:199-200), and the Thunder People can punish with lightning (Opler, 1941:240), live in the clouds and provide flint (Opler, 1941:38).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "Ultimately the dead person had to begin his journey to the land of the dead" (Opler, 1941:416).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Our concept is down, a place beneath. When I was a child, many years ago, the Chiricahua never talked about where other Indians go at death. They just talked about where their own people, the Chiricahua, go. We think of a dead person going on to another life—of his whole body, as it was on earth, going to the other world. He is really transferred to that other world" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:477).

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: "Our concept is down, a place beneath. When I was a child, many years ago, the Chiricahua never talked about where other Indians go at death. They just talked about where their own people, the Chiricahua, go. We think of a dead person going on to another life—of his whole body, as it was on earth, going to the other world. He is really transferred to that other world" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:477).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Notes: "Our concept is down, a place beneath. When I was a child, many years ago, the Chiricahua never talked about where other Indians go at death. They just talked about where their own people, the Chiricahua, go. We think of a dead person going on to another life—of his whole body, as it was on earth, going to the other world. He is really transferred to that other world" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:477).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: "The most obvious evidence that the Thunder People are displeased with an individual occurs when he is actually struck by lightning" (Opler, 1941:240).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: "There are a few creatures and supernaturals which are to be feared only if they are somehow offended. The horse and the mule, the spider, the Thunder People, and the Mountain People comprise this list" (Opler, 1941:239).

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "There are a few creatures and supernaturals which are to be feared only if they are somehow offended. The horse and the mule, the spider, the Thunder People, and the Mountain People comprise this list" (Opler, 1941:239).

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: "Insanity may be regarded as punishment for omission of necessary ritual gestures during the masked-dancer preparation . . ." (Opler, 1941:241).

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

— Yes

Notes: "Insanity may be regarded as punishment for omission of necessary ritual gestures during the masked-dancer preparation . . ." (Opler, 1941:241).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

— Yes

Notes: "Insanity may be regarded as punishment for omission of necessary ritual gestures during the masked-dancer preparation . . ." (Opler, 1941:241).

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

— Yes

Notes: "Ailments which do not yield to ordinary herbal remedies or to decoctions ritually administered are thought to have been contracted from unclean animals or from animals or supernaturals capable of sending disease when offended, defied, or instigated by malevolent forces. It is to combat sickness of this kind that the intricate curing ceremonies are reserved" (Opler, 1941:224).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

— Yes

Notes: "The Thunder People send lightning to punish some" (Opler, 1941:195).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

— Yes

Notes: "Insanity may be regarded as punishment for omission of necessary ritual gestures during the masked-dancer preparation . . ." (Opler, 1941:241).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

— Yes

Notes: "If people believe and learn his [the supernatural being Water Controller's] song, they can get rain" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:199).

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

— Yes

Notes: "If people believe and learn his [the supernatural being Water Controller's] song, they can get rain" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:199).

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: "If people believe and learn his [the supernatural being Water Controller's] song, they can get rain" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:199).

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: "If people believe and learn his [the supernatural being Water Controller's] song, they can get rain" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:199).

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: "If people believe and learn his [the supernatural being Water Controller's] song, they can get rain" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:199).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "The burial always takes place in the day, on the same day that death occurred if possible. They bury the corpse quickly and far from the settlements—in the mountains, if they are near" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:472).

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "The burial always takes place in the day, on the same day that death occurred if possible. They bury the corpse quickly and far from the settlements—in the mountains, if they are near" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:472).

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1850, Secondary Bone/Body Treatment, "secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur" (Schroeder, 2001; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: "... they kill the horse that has carried the dead person's possessions. It is stabbed in the throat or shot, at or near the grave" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:472).

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: ". . . they kill the horse that has carried the dead person's possessions. It is stabbed in the throat or shot, at or near the grave" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:472).

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: "The property they brought is buried with the corpse" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:473-474).

Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: "Usually for a man the only things that are buried with him are his clothes and weapons" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:474).

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: "Out there the members of the burial party might strike a little natural depression at the bottom of a hill. They could use this as a grave. . . If they find a little cave or a hole in the rocks, that is used. The body is put on the floor, and the entrance is blocked up with rocks and covered with mud to hide it and make it look like the side of the cliff. They aren't going to talk about the grave and tell where it is" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:473).

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of multiple centrally important virtues advocated by the Eastern Apache. See questions below for details.

Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Notes: "These things are impressed on [adolescent boys]: 'Don't be a coward; don't be untruthful; don't eat too much when you come back to camp between raids, or that will be your nature'" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:136).

Courage (in battle):

– Yes

Notes: "And they [parents and grandparents] tell the boys that, after coming home from a successful battle, their relatives and friends will be proud of them. Cowards are talked about, told nasty things before their faces, and are in disgrace" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:72).

Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: "It is customary to help the widows and the aged. If there are many such individuals and meat is scarce, the hunter may have little meat left upon his arrival at his own home" (Opler,

1941:323). Additionally, "a father caps advice to his son with this admonition: 'Do not be stingy and mean. Treat people right. Give half of what you have. Then you will be invited to feasts and get presents'" (Opler, 1941:399).

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Notes: "If I am going hunting with you, before we start out you might tell me, 'If I kill two deer for you, I'm going to kill a good fat one and it will be mine.' You must not show your selfishness in any way" (informant, quoted in Opler 1941:317).

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

Notes: "Since stoicism and strength are underlined, displays of personal consideration and 'softness' must be repressed" (Opler, 1941:74).

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "When a person is very sick and is unconscious, it is said that he is somewhere else, that his ghost has gone where the dead people are, to visit his friends. If he regains consciousness, it is because his ghost gets back again, and when he gets well he may tell where he was" (Opler, 1941:477).

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the spirit can travel separately from the body: "When a person is very sick and is unconscious, it is said that he is somewhere else, that his ghost has gone where the dead people are, to visit his friends. If he regains consciousness, it is because his ghost gets back again, and when he gets well he may tell where he was" (Opler, 1941:477).

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↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

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↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

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Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "The burial always takes place in the day, on the same day that death occurred if possible. They bury the corpse quickly and far from the settlements—in the mountains, if they are near" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:472).

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "The burial always takes place in the day, on the same day that death occurred if possible. They bury the corpse quickly and far from the settlements—in the mountains, if they are near" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:472).

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1850, Secondary Bone/Body Treatment, "secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur" (Schroeder, 2001; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: "... they kill the horse that has carried the dead person's possessions. It is stabbed in the throat or shot, at or near the grave" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:472).

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: "... they kill the horse that has carried the dead person's possessions. It is stabbed in the throat or shot, at or near the grave" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:472).

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: "The property they brought is buried with the corpse" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:473-474).

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: "Usually for a man the only things that are buried with him are his clothes and weapons" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:474).

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: "Out there the members of the burial party might strike a little natural depression at the bottom of a hill. They could use this as a grave. . . If they find a little cave or a hole in the rocks, that is used. The body is put on the floor, and the entrance is blocked up with rocks and covered with mud to hide it and make it look like the side of the cliff. They aren't going to talk about the grave and tell where it is" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:473).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that both previously human spirits and non-human supernatural beings are present (Opler, 1941:199, 302). See questions below for details.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: "The Chiricahua had a vague, personified belief in a supernatural being called 'Life Giver', who was sometimes pictured as a sky god. Occasionally prayers were directly addressed to him, but he was otherwise not involved in ceremonies" (Beierle, 2012:7).

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: "The Chiricahua had a vague, personified belief in a supernatural being called 'Life Giver', who was sometimes pictured as a sky god" (Beierle, 2012:7).

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, High Gods, a supreme high god is absent or not reported (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 34).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The ghosts are of two kinds—those of enemy peoples and those of tribesman (often of deceased relatives)" (Opler, 1941:302).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "... all owls are ghosts ..." (Opler, 1941:231). Because owls can be seen, it can be assumed that previously human spirits can be seen in some form.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "These 'words' of the owl can cause sickness through fright ..." (Opler, 1941:230).

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: Evidence indicates that previously human spirits remember where they lived: "Another story, so well known that it has been recorded from four different informants, concerns the return of a woman's ghost to her former home ..." (Opler, 1941:231).

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: "Owls [connected or equated with ghosts] talk the Chiricahua language. They say different things to different people" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:230).

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: "Owls [connected or equated with ghosts] talk the Chiricahua language. They say different things to different people" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:230).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "There are two other sets of supernaturals—the Mountain People and the Water Beings. The Mountain People are of more importance than any supernaturals so far mentioned, with the possible exception of Child of the Water and White Painted Woman" (Opler, 1941:199).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: Mountain People cannot be seen: "We hear words in there when we listen at cliffs or mountains, but we can't see the people" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:199). No ethnographic evidence indicates that other non-human supernatural beings can be seen.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "The Thunder People send lightning to punish some" (Opler, 1941:195).

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: "If people believe and learn his [Water Controller's] song, they can get rain" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:199).

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: "The Thunder People send lightning to punish some" (Opler, 1941:195).

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "However, fright [caused by the Thunder People] is again a powerful sickening agent: 'The scare harms you.' Lightning is said to be accompanied by an odor which comes from the powder or smoke that arises where it strikes. This powder, if it is inhaled, manifests itself in the ailment recognized as 'lightning sickness'" (Opler, 1941:240).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "The most obvious evidence that the Thunder People are displeased with an individual occurs when he is actually struck by lightning" (Opler, 1941:240).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that both previously human spirits and many different non-human supernatural beings are present. See Opler, 1941:199, 302 for more information.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: White Painted Woman is the mother of Child of the Water (referred to as the folk hero in the principal authority), who also has some type of kin relationship to Killer of Enemies, usually a brother. These supernatural beings are no longer considered active in human affairs (see Opler, 1941:197, 281).

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: The Mountain People protect the Eastern Apache from disease and enemies (Opler, 1941:267-268) and live in the mountains (Opler, 1941:35), the Water Beings have various powers associated with water (Opler, 1941:199-200), and the Thunder People can punish with lightning (Opler, 1941:240), live in the clouds and provide flint (Opler, 1941:38).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: "The most obvious evidence that the Thunder People are displeased with an individual occurs when he is actually struck by lightning" (Opler, 1941:240).

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: "'If you don't worship them in the right way, you should be frightened.' . . . The restrictions are obeyed, not from fear of the power of those dancing [impersonating the Mountain Spirits], but because 'the real Mountain Spirits could bring on sickness or death if these things were violated'" (Opler, 1941:112).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: "The most obvious evidence that the Thunder People are displeased with an individual occurs when he is actually struck by lightning" (Opler, 1941:240).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: "There are a few creatures and supernaturals which are to be feared only if they are somehow offended. The horse and the mule, the spider, the Thunder People, and the Mountain People comprise this list" (Opler, 1941:239).

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "There are a few creatures and supernaturals which are to be feared only if they are somehow offended. The horse and the mule, the spider, the Thunder People, and the Mountain People comprise this list" (Opler, 1941:239).

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: "Insanity may be regarded as punishment for omission of necessary ritual gestures during the masked-dancer preparation . . ." (Opler, 1941:241).

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: "Insanity may be regarded as punishment for omission of necessary ritual gestures during the masked-dancer preparation . . ." (Opler, 1941:241).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: "Insanity may be regarded as punishment for omission of necessary ritual gestures during the masked-dancer preparation . . ." (Opler, 1941:241).

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Ailments which do not yield to ordinary herbal remedies or to decoctions ritually administered are thought to have been contracted from unclean animals or from animals or supernaturals capable of sending disease when offended, defied, or instigated by malevolent forces. It is to combat sickness of this kind that the intricate curing ceremonies are reserved" (Opler, 1941:224).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: "The Thunder People send lightning to punish some" (Opler, 1941:195).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: "Insanity may be regarded as punishment for omission of necessary ritual gestures during the masked-dancer preparation . . ." (Opler, 1941:241).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: "If people believe and learn his [the supernatural being Water Controller's] song, they can get rain" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:199).

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Notes: "If people believe and learn his [the supernatural being Water Controller's] song, they can get rain" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:199).

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: "If people believe and learn his [the supernatural being Water Controller's] song, they can get rain" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:199).

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: "If people believe and learn his [the supernatural being Water Controller's] song, they can get rain" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:199).

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: "If people believe and learn his [the supernatural being Water Controller's] song, they can get rain" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:199).

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "In the eyes of his fellows the moral person is one who heeds the social conventions and discharges his obligations in obedience to the tribal ethic" (Opler, 1941:458).

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of multiple centrally important virtues advocated by the Eastern Apache. See questions below for details.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Notes: "These things are impressed on [adolescent boys]: 'Don't be a coward; don't be untruthful; don't eat too much when you come back to camp between raids, or that will be your nature'" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:136).

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

Notes: "And they [parents and grandparents] tell the boys that, after coming home from a successful battle, their relatives and friends will be proud of them. Cowards are talked about, told nasty things before their faces, and are in disgrace" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:72).

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: "It is customary to help the widows and the aged. If there are many such individuals and meat is scarce, the hunter may have little meat left upon his arrival at his own home" (Opler, 1941:323). Additionally, "a father caps advice to his son with this admonition: 'Do not be stingy and mean. Treat people right. Give half of what you have. Then you will be invited to feasts and get presents'" (Opler, 1941:399).

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Notes: "If I am going hunting with you, before we start out you might tell me, 'If I kill two deer for you, I'm going to kill a good fat one and it will be mine.' You must not show your selfishness in any way" (informant, quoted in Opler 1941:317).

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

Notes: "Since stoicism and strength are underlined, displays of personal consideration and 'softness' must be repressed" (Opler, 1941:74).

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: "An Apache boy is trained not to pay too much attention to the women. It is not considered manly. The Apache girl is expected to be reserved, and a show of affection in public between the sexes is laughed at" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:78).

Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: "There is also a very strict rule against a novice having sexual intercourse while he is out" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:137).

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: "'Don't eat before you go out on the hunt' they would say. 'Even though you have plenty in camp, don't eat in the morning before you go out. Go out and hunt with an empty stomach. Then Yusun [the deity also referred to as Life Giver] will pity you'" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:316).

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that there are multiple food taboos present depending on a person's age, status, and health. See Opler, 1941:137, 211, 265 for more information.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: While permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations are not required, ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of scarring practices to prevent persecution by previously human spirits: "By scarring your nose with a live coal, you keep ghosts away. You take a burning stick, wet it at one end, fix this end on your nose, and let it burn down so that it scars your nose. Then the ghost will fear you and keep away" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:302).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the power that allows shamans to perform ceremonies can also demand sacrifices of the shaman's relatives: "He [a shaman] might cure in a good way, but when the power demands a relative, he has to sacrifice one to protect himself" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:256).

Other:

– Yes [specify]: Kin of religious specialists

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the power that allows shamans to perform ceremonies can also demand sacrifices of the shaman's relatives: "He [a shaman] might cure in a good way, but when the power demands a relative, he has to sacrifice one to protect himself" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:256).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the power that allows shamans to perform ceremonies can also demand sacrifices of the shaman's relatives, including their children: "He [a shaman] allows the power to take [sacrifice] his son, his daughter, his wife, or any other close relative" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:256).

Other:

– Yes [specify]: Kin of religious specialists

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the power that allows shamans to perform ceremonies can also demand sacrifices of the shaman's relatives, including their children: "He [a shaman] allows the power to take [sacrifice] his son, his daughter, his wife, or any other close relative" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:256).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: "These offerings [given to the shaman before the ceremony] are almost always four in number and are generally of such a nature that they can be directly employed at some stage in the rite. Among those which commonly appear are turquoise, abalone shell, eagle feathers, pollen, specular iron ore, unblemished buckskin, black flint blades, white shell, and obsidian" (Opler, 1941:259).

To other in-group members:

– Yes

Notes: "Before the ceremony can begin, and usually at the time of the request, ceremonial gifts are tendered the shaman. These are gifts to the power to assure its co-operation" (Opler, 1941:259).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that prayer is a significant aspect of religious practices, especially during ceremonies (see Opler, 1941:94, 107-108, 262 for details) and by shamans (see Opler, 1941:262, 283, 304-305 for details).

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: Boys of a certain age are expected to become novices and learn raiding and warfare: "But raiding in enemy country is hazardous work at best, and sometimes the raiders, when they go forward on a particularly dangerous mission, must leave the novice at a distance so that he will not be drawn into battle. Then, if they encounter difficulties or superior forces, they may be unable to reach him again. Novices deserted in this way have perished or have suffered great hardship before reaching their homes" (Opler, 1941:139).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that many private and small-scale rituals take place at or near birth (Opler, 1941:6-18) as well as for healing purposes (see Opler, 1941:216-267 for details).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: The puberty rite for girls is a large-scale ritual with multiple religious elements attended by many individuals: "The rite itself has become the focal point for a complex of events—social, economic, and ritual" (Opler, 1941:82). See Opler, 1941:82-134 for more information.

Is there use of intoxicants:

– I don't know

Notes: While there is reference to smoking, it is unknown whether the substance smoked leads to an altered state of consciousness: "After about six songs they have a smoking song. They smoke after this song; all those inside can smoke then" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:118).

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that many extra-ritual in-group markers are present. See questions below for details.

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

— Yes

Notes: "The men tattoo themselves but limit the area to the inner part of the arms . . . Women tattoo also. In addition to tattoo markings on the arms, they place a dot on either cheek and often a figure, such as a circle or a wavy or serrated line, on the forehead" (Opler, 1941:21-22).

↳ Food taboos:

— Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that there are multiple food taboos present depending on a person's age, status, and health. See Opler, 1941:137, 211, 265 for more information.

↳ Hair:

— Yes

Notes: "We all wear long hair. A person doesn't dare cut his hair off with a knife. He has to take good care of his hair. To cut it brings bad luck. The only time you do that is when a member of your family has died" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:20). Additionally, "A man leaves his hair unbraided. He pushes it to the sides, out of his eyes and over his shoulders, and it is held in place by a band which crosses his forehead" (Opler, 1941:20).

↳ Dress:

— Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the Eastern Apache have traditional clothing unique to their society. See Opler, 1941:19-22 for details.

↳ Ornaments:

— Yes

Notes: "When the baby is from a week to a few months old, his mother or his maternal grandmother pierces his ears. . . Pendants of white beads or turquoise are strung from the ears of very young children, and this mode of ornamentation continues throughout life" (Opler, 1941:13).

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

— Yes

Notes: The girls' puberty rite creates a close and lasting fictive kin relationship between the girl undergoing the rite and the woman attending her: "Right from this time the girl calls that woman 'mother,' even though she is no relative, and this woman calls the girl 'my daughter'" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:84). A similar process occurs with the singer chosen for the ceremony: "If you [referring to the grandfather of the girl undergoing the puberty rite] choose one of these men, you are brother to him all your life, even if you are not related to him. . . He thinks of your children as his children" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:85).

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

— Yes

Notes: The girls' puberty rite creates a close and lasting fictive kin relationship between the girl undergoing the rite and the woman attending her. A similar process occurs with the singer chosen for the ceremony. Because the puberty rite is performed for all girls, these relationships are assumed to be widespread. See question above for more information, as well as Opler, 1941:84-85.

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

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Notes: "An Apache boy is trained not to pay too much attention to the women. It is not considered manly. The Apache girl is expected to be reserved, and a show of affection in public between the sexes is laughed at" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:78).

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Food taboos:

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Dress:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the Eastern Apache have traditional clothing unique to their society. See Opler, 1941:19-22 for details.

Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: "When the baby is from a week to a few months old, his mother or his maternal grandmother pierces his ears. . . Pendants of white beads or turquoise are strung from the ears of very young children, and this mode of ornamentation continues throughout life" (Opler, 1941:13).

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Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: The girls' puberty rite creates a close and lasting fictive kin relationship between the girl undergoing the rite and the woman attending her. A similar process occurs with the singer chosen for the ceremony. Because the puberty rite is performed for all girls, these relationships are assumed to be widespread. See question above for more information, as well as Opler, 1941:84-85.

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Notes: The Eastern Apache do not have jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community (SCCS Variable 237, Jurisdictional Hierarchy Beyond Local Community; retrieved from Divale, 2004). Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 10: Descent) indicate that the Eastern Apache have bilateral descent without kindreds. Additionally, the Eastern Apache live in agamous communities without localized clans, lineal kin groups, or exogamy (Murdock, 1962-1971, columns 19, 20, 22). Information on jurisdictional hierarchy and kin ties indicates that the Eastern Apache are most accurately characterized as a band.

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of formal education during the time focus of this entry.

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: During the time focus of this entry, the Eastern Apache did not have jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of a band (SCCS Variable 237, Jurisdictional Hierarchy Beyond Local Community; retrieved from Divale, 2004). See question above regarding levels of social complexity.

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of taxes or tithes.

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 90, Police, the Eastern Apache do not have a specialized police force (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Because the religious group is coterminous with the society itself, this entry assumes that the religious group provides food for itself. The Eastern Apache depend primarily on gathering (SCCS Variable 203, Dependence on Gathering), with hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting) as a secondary means of subsistence (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 7).

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

Notes: The Eastern Apache depend primarily on gathering (SCCS Variable 203, Dependence on Gathering), with hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting) as a secondary means of subsistence (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 7).

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 149, Scale 1 [of Cultural Complexity] - Writing and Records, mnemonic devices are utilized, but no writing or records specific to the religious group (Murdock and Provost, 1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: "The preoccupation with the growth of wild plants is reflected in the attitude toward the seasons and in the names of the principal time periods. Besides the four seasons, six time periods, beginning with the first signs of spring, divide the year. Their names, in order, are: 'Little Eagles,' 'Many Leaves,' 'Large Leaves,' 'Large Fruit,' 'Earth Is Reddish Brown,' and 'Ghost Face'" (Opler, 1941:354).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

— No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of formal education during the time focus of this entry.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

— I don't know

Notes: "The woman must keep on hand a plentiful supply of water for drinking, cooking, and washing. She brings it from a near-by spring or stream in a pitch-covered basketry jar" (Opler, 1941:376).

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: ". . . many Chiricahua refused to obey the [U.S. military] order to move. Others who were forced to go would leave their new home as soon as military supervision was relaxed. Out of this situation grew a number of bloody incidents and two major military operations . . ." (Opler, 1941:2).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

— I don't know

Notes: Councils to judge accusations of wrongdoing appear to be present, but it is not clear the extent to which they are institutionalized: "When something wrong which affects the whole group occurs, the leader calls in the people involved, or the important men, or even all the people. For witchcraft, a council of this sort would be held. The case would be presented, and the influential men would decide on the punishment" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:252).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

— I don't know

Notes: Providing care for the elderly appears to be present but it is not clear the extent to which it is institutionalized: "It is customary to help the widows and the aged" (Opler, 1941:323).

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

— I don't know

Notes: Enforcing punishment appears to be present, but it is not clear the extent to which it is institutionalized: "If two persons committed incest and were found out, a crowd would gather, and any headman would say, 'I know those two had intercourse together; get them!' Everyone considered them

witches, and they were burned. Incest sometimes goes before a council of people and sometimes the parents kill them outright" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:250).

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: "[Social customs] aren't laws—they are so strong we don't need laws. A person is supposed to keep certain customs" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:458).

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Notes: The Eastern Apache do not have jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community (SCCS Variable 237, Jurisdictional Hierarchy Beyond Local Community; retrieved from Divale, 2004). Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 10: Descent) indicate that the Eastern Apache have bilateral descent without kindreds. Additionally, the Eastern Apache live in agamous communities without localized clans, lineal kin groups, or exogamy (Murdock, 1962-1971, columns 19, 20, 22). Information on jurisdictional hierarchy and kin ties indicates that the Eastern Apache are most accurately characterized as a band.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– I don't know

Notes: Providing care for the elderly appears to be present but it is not clear the extent to which it is institutionalized: "It is customary to help the widows and the aged" (Opler, 1941:323).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of formal education during the time focus of this entry.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of formal education during the time focus of this entry.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: During the time focus of this entry, the Eastern Apache did not have jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of a band (SCCS Variable 237, Jurisdictional Hierarchy Beyond Local Community; retrieved from Divale, 2004). See question above regarding levels of social complexity.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– I don't know

Notes: "The woman must keep on hand a plentiful supply of water for drinking, cooking, and washing. She brings it from a near-by spring or stream in a pitch-covered basketry jar" (Opler, 1941:376).

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of taxes or tithes.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 90, Police, the Eastern Apache do not have a specialized police force (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– I don't know

Notes: Councils to judge accusations of wrongdoing appear to be present, but it is not clear the extent to which they are institutionalized: "When something wrong which affects the whole group occurs, the leader calls in the people involved, or the important men, or even all the people. For witchcraft, a council of this sort would be held. The case would be presented, and the influential men would decide on the punishment" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:252).

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– I don't know

Notes: Enforcing punishment appears to be present, but it is not clear the extent to which it is institutionalized: "If two persons committed incest and were found out, a crowd would gather, and any headman would say, 'I know those two had intercourse together; get them!' Everyone considered them witches, and they were burned. Incest sometimes goes before a council of people and sometimes the parents kill them outright" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:250).

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: "[Social customs] aren't laws—they are so strong we don't need laws. A person is supposed to keep certain customs" (informant, quoted in Opler, 1941:458).

Warfare

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: ". . . many Chiricahua refused to obey the [U.S. military] order to move. Others who were forced to go would leave their new home as soon as military supervision was relaxed. Out of this situation grew a number of bloody incidents and two major military operations . . ." (Opler, 1941:2).

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 149, Scale 1 [of Cultural Complexity] - Writing and Records, mnemonic devices are utilized, but no writing or records specific to the religious group (Murdock and Provost, 1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: "The preoccupation with the growth of wild plants is reflected in the attitude toward the seasons and in the names of the principal time periods. Besides the four seasons, six time periods,

beginning with the first signs of spring, divide the year. Their names, in order, are: 'Little Eagles,' 'Many Leaves,' 'Large Leaves,' 'Large Fruit,' 'Earth Is Reddish Brown,' and 'Ghost Face'" (Opler, 1941:354).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Because the religious group is coterminous with the society itself, this entry assumes that the religious group provides food for itself. The Eastern Apache depend primarily on gathering (SCCS Variable 203, Dependence on Gathering), with hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting) as a secondary means of subsistence (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 7).

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

Notes: The Eastern Apache depend primarily on gathering (SCCS Variable 203, Dependence on Gathering), with hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting) as a secondary means of subsistence (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 7).